

THEIA^{XR} NEWSLETTER

ISSUE No. 3

UPDATE ON THEIA^{XR}

Here is the third issue of the THEIA^{XR} Newsletter, which aims to keep you up to date in our project. The latest status of our activities and insights into the many events and meetings that took place in the past half year. In addition, we have reached the halftime point of the project and have mastered our first review meeting a few days ago. We are looking forward keeping you updated with this third issue and invite you to continue following our journey to make the invisible visible.

Martijn Rooker, THEIA^{XR} project coordinator states:

“Some major events have taken place in the last period of the project! First, we had our third consortium meeting taking place in Tampere, Finland visiting the site of the Reach Stacker use case location and learning more about how XR can be of support in remote operation. Furthermore, the mid-term review meeting has taken place, where we had to present our current results to the European Commission and technical experts. It was great to experience that we are processing in the right direction, and we can make a large impact with the developments taking place within the project. The results of the review meeting have given us even more motivation supporting mobile machine operators in the daily work!”

THEIA^{XR} TECHNICAL RESULTS

Author: [Clemens Arth](#), TU Graz

Our current focus is on the combination of digital light processing (DLP) with our laser projection system, to further enrich the portfolio of possible visualizations in outdoor scenarios. The major problem with regular

DLP projectors is the brightness created and also the induced costs. Furthermore, LED technology is mandatory, as gas-lamp driven systems are doomed to break almost immediately through vibrations or physical shakes, common to machine-mounted systems.

Our approach is to use low-cost projectors and adapt them to increase brightness significantly. One option is to include larger LED panels, which in turn generate a lot of heat which has to

dissipate somehow. In Figure 1 an upgraded projector is shown, supposed to triple the emanating light. The proper function and the calibration to register the device properly in the context of the laser projection system has yet to be tested.

Figure 1: Upgraded laser projector with additional cooling assembly on the left, original consumer projector on the right

Another avenue currently investigated is the use of radar technology to localize infrastructure. By using radio waves, we should be able to detect metal structures and other assemblies at a short distance below graceful surfaces, such as snow, for example. The underlying technology comes from the area of ground penetrating radar, however, to build a cost-effective we need to more closely understand the physical phenomena encountered through a variety of antennas, emanating and absorbing radio waves. The status is that there is an early prototype available, tests to investigate the usefulness and constructing a proper physical assembly, together with an intuitive visualization and user interface are tasks still pending. Figure 2 shows the early-stage development, subject to further improvements in the coming months.

Figure 2: Early-stage prototype for sensing infrastructure using radio waves

UPDATES FROM OUR USE CASES

Spotlight “Excavator”

Author: [Volker Waurich](#), TU Dresden – Chair of Construction Machinery

During the first half of the project, novel visualization technologies have been developed to support the operator in the excavator cabin. Three scenarios are in the focus of the excavator use case: 1) finish grading with a machine control system, 2) person detection in the vicinity of the machine and 3) model based earth moving. An LED-matrix display visualizes the height derivation during work directly in the field of view of the operator. AI-cameras detect persons in the surrounding of the machine and indicate the risk of the potential collisions with an ambient light around the front facing window. For the last use case, a textured 3d-representation of the surrounding is generated with a lidar and a camera in order to create a clear reference between virtual model and real environment.

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These prototype technologies are the basis of the THEIA^{XR} visualization concept for the excavator. In order to present the ideas and the implementation to a bright audience, the THEIA^{XR} concept has been submitted for the innovation award of the world's leading fair for construction machinery, *bauma 2025*.

We are delighted to be among the finalists in the category “research”.

This fair is the most important event of the industry and we will demonstrate the THEIA^{XR} showcase on the TU-Dresden booth. As we are one of the finalists, we have the opportunity to present our concept to a wide audience during the fair.

Since we have the prototypes available, we already presented the technologies to operators and specialists in the field of construction machinery. During several live-demos with our excavator in Dresden, we got valuable opinions and positive feedback about our approaches to enhance the HMI of excavators.

Figure 3: 9th International VDI Conference: Connected Off-Highway Machinery

Figure 4: HMI Lab prototype

Besides this, the preliminary results of the THEIA^{XR} uses case have been presented on industrial events e.g. *VDI-Connected Off-Highway Machinery* or *Fachtagung Baumaschinentechnik*.

While presenting intermediate results and prototypes, we are already working on improving, redesigning and enhancing the current solutions. In the HMI-Lab, novel concepts for physical HMI-components or digital interfaces can be prototyped and tested rapidly. One additional information that is very valuable during excavator operation is the location of underground media. Credits to our student Tim Breitbarth who is working on HMI-concepts for underground media visualization.

Figure 5: Redesigned interface for the main display

PAST MEETINGS AND EVENTS

MARCH 2024: WORKSHOPS IN GLACHAU

End user integration is a central element in the THEIA^{XR} development strategy. Therefore, Manuel Kulzer, Stuttgart Media University, visited operators of excavators to get their direct input.

For two co-design workshops in the construction use-case, he visited the training grounds of the ÜAZ Glauchau. One workshop with apprentices currently in their third year of apprenticeship, and one with the trainers, some of them with 20+ years of experience on construction sites.

He wanted to hear what they think about the cabin technology ideas we had already come up with and what else they would like to see in the excavator cabin of the future. In the end, a long list of comments, many ideas that were approved, one that was discarded (and that's okay), and several new ones, one of them a real "game changer" according to operators, came out of the workshop.

During lunch break, he even got to meet and chat with [Thomas jr Schlüter](#), product manager at one of the largest construction machine distributors of Germany. There are definitely some things we could learn from each other.

Figure 6: Impressions from the workshop in Glauchau

Figure 7: Impressions from the workshop in Glauchau

MARCH 2024:

Also in March, there was a first workshop with [Professur für Baumaschinen](#) and [Technisches Design | td](#) on implementing cabin illumination into the HMI.

Light indicators around the front window and the main display are intended to inform the operator about the direction, distance, and collision risk of obstacles near the machine. Using our modular and multimodal prototyping cab, it was exciting to try out different feedback setups. The colleagues tested different mappings using color, animations, and position of the lights to convey information, aiming to improve perception, attention control, and distraction.

Credits to [Richard Morgenstern](#), who implemented the HMI setup and developed the various concepts as part of his diploma thesis.

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Figure 8: Cabin illumination in HMI

APRIL 2024: MOUNTAINPLANET

THEIA^{XR} was represented at the MountainPlanet on the stand of [Prinoth](#). Interested people could come by and dive more into snowgrooming and extended reality in the cabin.

Figure 9: THEIA^{XR} represented at the Prinoth stand

APRIL 2024: TESTING DAYS

Testing days are a great opportunity to put the concepts developed into action. As it was done on an actual snowgroomer at the Prinoth headquarters in Sterzing, Italy. Accompanying us were three novel prototypes:

- a novel laser-camera setup,
- a camera-based spotlight system,
- and a panoramic thermal camera.

The main objective was to push the boundaries of our hardware and collect valuable data within the harsh Alpine environment.

Figure 10: Testing equipment on the snow groomer

The observations during the testing revealed promising results for these prototypes, underscoring their potential to assist operators in demanding situations. Besides CAN-bus recordings and precise 3D reconstructions from the testing region, the colleagues were able to gather experience and identify potential shortcomings that would not have been apparent through data alone. These findings will prove invaluable for future field trips and our overall understanding of the project's requirements and challenges.

Figure 11: Programming

Departing from South Tyrol, the participants carried not only valuable data but also experience and optimism to continue the development of our prototypes. Thanks a lot, to Prinoth for their great support and hospitality during the stay!

Figure 12: Testing equipment inside the snow groomer

MAY 2024: REACHSTACKER TESTING

At the Tampere test yard by Kalmar, tests with a 360° camera took place.

The camera was installed on top of a terminal tractor to demonstrate the fast movement of the

machine with the target. It was important to check how videos can be transferred over 5G network to a control station and how big is the latency. Furthermore, it was used to evaluate the user experience; when utilizing a monitor or VR headset, respectively how big are the differences and how to utilize these.

The insights gained are now further used in the work on the use case.

Figure 13: Reachstacker testing

MAY 2024: LESSONS LEARNED

Lessons learned: participating in EU projects THEIA^{XR} was one of the examples of projects when [Pekka Yli-Paunu](#) was sharing his experience with EU funded projects to Finnish SMEs and representatives from Large Enterprises in a regional event in Tampere.

In his presentation, Pekka was covering the entire process from reasons to participate over the proposal phase to the now running execution of the project. The group size allowed interesting discussions among the participants who were not (yet) active in Horizon Europe or similar programs.

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Figure 14: Pekka Yli-Paunu at his presentation

JUNE 2024: CONSORTIUM MEETING

We cannot believe it ourselves, but in June of 2024 it was already time for the project's 3rd consortium meeting.

The meeting took place in Tampere, Finland, and was hosted by VTT, Kalmar und Creanex. These meetings are always a blast. Partners come together and share the status of their work as well as show results they have already gotten. Being guests at these institutions, we also got the opportunity to get active with demonstrators. A big thank you to all the colleagues hosting us in the beautiful and sunny city of Tampere.

Figure 15: Group picture at the consortium meeting

JUNE 2024: IVT EXPO

For the second time, the project was very present at the IVT Expo in Köln, Germany, at the booth of the project coordinator [TTControl](#). Thanks to all the colleagues, who represented the project and all interested visitors for stopping by.

Figure 16: THEIA^{XR} represented at the TTControl stand at the IVT Expo

Figure 17: THEIA^{XR} represented at the TTControl stand at the IVT Expo

JUNE 2024: WSCG

At the International Conference on Computer Graphics, Visualization and Computer Vision (WSCG) our colleagues Mika Heinemann, Thomas Kernbauer, Philipp Fleck and [Clemens Arth](#) from [Technische Universität Graz](#) were able

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to present their paper on "Spotlight Control for Real-Time Targeting". It is worth the read, the whole paper can be found on our website and on [Zenodo](#).

AUGUST 2024: PODCAST

THEIA^{XR} goes podcast!

In August our coordinator, [Martijn Rooker](#) from [TTControl](#), and [Stephan Grad](#) from [Exciting Tech](#), had an insightful discussion about the THEIA^{XR} project. They delved into our activities and the impact we're aiming to achieve. The episode is available at "[Exciting Tech](#)" podcast in German.

Special thanks to Stephan for the invitation—participating was a pleasure!

Figure 18: Stephan Grad and Martijn Rooker at the recording of the podcast

SEPTEMBER 2024: REVIEW MEETING

Half way the project, it was time to present our results so far to the European Commission and the technical experts during the midterm review. This event took place on 12th September. After long preparation including organizing presentations and project videos, we presented during the whole day our results and had intense discussions with the experts about the applicability of our solutions and how they can make an impact in the off-highway domain. The result was a very interesting meeting with many discussions, constructive and positive

feedback with respect to our work, but also enough recommendations on how to continue and make a more lasting impact. We want to thank the European Commission and the technical experts for the interaction and their feedback. It was great to hear that we are on the right track and we are more motivated than ever to continue working in this fascinating domain.

Figure 19: Online midterm review meeting

SEPTEMBER 2024: VDI CONFERENCE

Sebastian Lorenz and Volker Waurich from TU Dresden introduced and presented THEIA^{XR} at the VDI Conference in Munich, Germany.

Figure 20: THEIA^{XR} at the VDI conference

It was a pleasure to present our approaches to Extended Reality interaction at the 9th international VDI Conference on Connected Off-Highway-Machines. Our presentation advanced the perspective on augmenting technologies suitable for machine operation use cases and fostered discussions about data availability and operator integration

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in digitalized and connected production systems.

HONORED PAPERS

We are very proud of all the papers that have been issued for the THEIA^{XR} project and even more of those, who have been recognised and rewarded with an award. Three papers have achieved this honour, which we will introduce in this section. Congratulations to the authors of these great papers!

COMING UP

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